

Script Interview

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1 Interview Script

1.1 Warm-up

- How long have you been with the Recod.ai research laboratory?
- Are you a professor, postdoctoral researcher, graduate, or undergraduate student?
- How many and in which software development (system) projects based on Artificial Intelligence have you participated or worked in the laboratory?
- Can you describe, in general terms, the nature of the projects you have participated in? By nature, we mean domain, problems, and size/scale.

1.2 Contextualization

- How many people work in the project teams?
- How does communication work between the team?
- What is the role of each of these people?
- What challenges do you face in the context of Recod.ai when performing your role in these projects?

1.3 Process Questions

- What are the main activities carried out in the projects you work (or worked) on, in general?
- Can you sketch an outline of the process (Jamboard/Slides)?
- What are your main activities in this research project(s)? What are your responsibilities in this research project(s)?

- What are the main artifacts generated and delivered to partner companies?
- What methods, techniques, and practices do you use to perform activities in the projects?
- What could be improved or needs to be modified in these processes?
- What technical challenges do you face in the context of these projects?
- How do you perceive the interweaving of software development and DS activities?
- Is software quality prioritized in the projects?
- What software quality characteristics (attributes) do you prioritize in the context of these DS projects?
- Could you give examples of these prioritized characteristics?